

Distributed Cost-Based Scheduling in Cloud Computing Environment

Rupali, Anil Kumar Jaiswal

Abstract—Cloud computing can be defined as one of the prominent technologies that lets a user change, configure and access the services online. It can be said that this is a prototype of computing that helps in saving cost and time of a user practically the use of cloud computing can be found in various fields like education, health, banking etc. Cloud computing is an internet dependent technology thus it is the major responsibility of Cloud Service Providers (CSPs) to care of data stored by user at data centers. Scheduling in cloud computing environment plays a vital role as to achieve maximum utilization and user satisfaction cloud providers need to schedule resources effectively. Job scheduling for cloud computing is analyzed in the following work. To complete, recreate the task calculation, and conveyed scheduling methods CloudSim3.0.3 is utilized. This research work discusses the job scheduling for circulated processing condition also by exploring on this issue we find it works with minimum time and less cost. In this work two load balancing techniques have been employed: ‘Throttled stack adjustment policy’ and ‘Active VM load balancing policy’ with two brokerage services ‘Advanced Response Time’ and ‘Reconfigure Dynamically’ to evaluate the VM_Cost, DC_Cost, Response Time, and Data Processing Time. The proposed techniques are compared with Round Robin scheduling policy.

Keywords—Physical machines, virtual machines, support for repetition, self-healing, highly scalable programming model.

I. INTRODUCTION

CLOUD environment charging pay per use from the cloud clients over the internet and is entitled by virtualization and the abstraction technology. The name cloud computing came from the cloud symbol that is most commonly used to characterize the Internet in flow charts and diagrams. Cloud Service providers and cloud end-users are the key players for the cloud estimating paradigm. Based upon the changing necessities of the cloud infrastructure focused on providing the computing environment to end user with QOS (Quality of Service) and make profits for the cloud service providers [3]. So this environment is a distributed model spread over the large scale which is providing the on-demand services such as non-interfering resource pooling, rapid elasticity and location independence with the help of virtualization support and hides the details of system implementation from cloud users with abstraction support [1]. Cloud is a virtualized pool of computing resources. It can:

Rupali is an Assistant Professor at the Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Maharishi Ved Vyas engineering college, Jagadhri, Yamuna agar, Haryana, India (e-mail: Rupali.sharma514@gmail.com).

Assistant Professor, Department of mechanical Engineering, Surya Group of Anil Kumar is with the Maharishi Markandeshwar University, Institute of Mohanlal Ganj, Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh, India (e-mail: ak38127@gmail.com).

- [1] Manage a variety of different workload, including the batch of back-end operations and user-oriented interactive applications.
- [2] Rapidly setup and increase workload by immediate providing physical machines or virtual machines.
- [3] Support for repetition, self-healing, and highly scalable programming model, so that workload can be recovered from a variety of unavoidable hardware and software failure.
- [4] This minimization process is carried out by matching the task with most suitable resources. The issue in scheduling is that the logical sequence of task must be preserved.
- [5] The scheduler must be capable of upholding total execution time as well as the monetary cost, which can only be attained by using a better scheduling algorithm. Virtualization Technology has been utilized progressively broadly in current data centers keeping in mind the end goal to enhance its vitality proficiency.

II. RELATED WORK

In [1] the author represents job scheduling centered on two Heuristic approaches i.e. MQS (Multi-queue job scheduling) and ACO (Ant colony optimization) in cloud atmosphere and then relating these two methodologies in view of factor of energy and time [1]

In [2], the author runs a better credit-based scheduling algorithm by means of the constraints like user priority, task length and deadline constraints. The new results show a significant improvement in the consumption of resources with speedy response time [2].

In [3] a Load Balanced Min-Min (LBMM) algorithm is projected by the journalist that cuts the make span and rises the resource utilization. The projected system has two-phases. In the first phase the old-style Min-Min algorithm is implemented and in the second phase the jobs are rearranged to use the unused resources efficiently. Grid computing is a kind of distributed computing which inhabits the combined and two-way use of distributed resources [3].

In [4], Chawda and Chakraborty presented a better load balancing algorithm taking Min-Min algorithm as base in order to decrease the makespan and rise the resource utilization (ILBMM). The estimated method has two different stages, in the first stage old-style min-min algorithm is executed and in second stage it selects the task with maximum achievement time and allocates it to suitable source to yield improved makespan and utilize resource effectively [4].

In [8], Mukundha et al. planned an idea named Load balancing scheduling algorithm for the cloud networks via

Software Defined Networks (SDN). This algorithm mechanism on the basis of identical circulation of client requests to all the regions accessible by the specific cloud networks [8].

Ajmire chiefly puts emphases on capture and recovery of the internal state of process, including the execution and data state – activation history, and static and heap challenge to scheme an effective scheduling policy to attain maximum performance in cloud computing [7].

Suri and Rani deliberate priority-based scheduling method on mixed resources in cloud computing grounded upon PERT skill. This scheduling ideal reduces the accomplishment time, make span [9].

Dhiraviam and Raj presented a copy of agreeable cloud computing amongst examination foundations and colleges using Virtual Cloud ideas. The mentioned prototype of Two-Way Cloud Computing includes the ideas of cloud league and volunteer registering and is concentrated around our Virtual Cloud building design [10].

Alipori, and Javadi boon a fresh method based on building the length of the critical path littler and reducing cost of communication. As a final point, the results gained from execution of the presented method show that this algorithm performs same as other algorithms when it faces with graphs deprived of communication cost. It does earlier and improved than some algorithms like DSC and MCP algorithms when it faces with the graphs involving communication cost [5].

Oesterle et al. presented use situation setups with a wide range of meteorological solicitations from operative research studies. They extend available high-performance computing ideas and permit for simple and scattered computing supplements, powerful and cost-effective contact to computing capacity [6].

III. PROBLEM ANALYSIS

Critical piece of cloud computing is job scheduling. Task scheduling is a mapping method from client's resources to the fitting determination of assets and its execution. By utilizing the innovation of virtualization, every single physical device is virtualized and translucent for clients. All clients have their own virtual device, these gadgets don't associate with each other and they are made in view of clients' prerequisites [5]. Also, at least one virtual machine can keep running on a solitary host PC so that the use rate of assets has been viably moved forward. Job scheduling and arranging of assets are primary issue parts in cloud computing. A few Cloud suppliers are accessible everyone offering distinctive valuing models and situated in various geographic districts [7]. Another worry is choosing suppliers and server farm areas for applications. In this manner there is a need that empowers designers to assess necessities of expansive scale Cloud applications as far as geographic dissemination of both registering servers and client workloads.

IV. PROPOSED WORK

In the work, two VM stack adjusting systems are executed.

[1] Throttled stack adjusting strategy that restricts the quantity of solicitations being prepared in each virtual machine to a throttling limit. On the off chance that solicitations are gotten making this edge be surpassed in all accessible virtual machines, at that point the solicitations are lined until the point that a virtual machine ends up plainly accessible. Each VM is designated just a single undertaking at any given moment and can be assigned another task just when the present task has finished [10]. The Throttled VM Load Balancer does not actualize any task lining usefulness but rather restores a legitimate VM id just if accessible. The Throttled VM Load Balancer executes CloudSim Event Listener to get advised of the VM's being designated and arranged for by the Datacenter Controller [5].

[2] Active VM Load Balancer stack adjusts the duties among nearby VM's in a method to attempt and out the quantity of dynamic task at any given time on each VM. Determine the VM with a minimum number of allocations [4]. On the off chance that all accessible VMs are not dispensed, assigned the new ones.

In addition, a brokerage policy for highest load sharing is implemented which tries to cut the load of a data center with other data centers whenever the original data center's performance worsens above a pre-defined onset value.

V. RESULTS

In this, it displays the proposed scheduling systems. In this, it takes the distinctive situations like Optimize Response Time and Reconfigure Dynamically.

The outcomes figured for above arrangements on three data centers and two financier benefit strategies to be specific Optimize Response Time and Reconfigure Dynamically under three scheduling approaches to be specific Round Robin, Equally Spread and Throttled are finished up in tables underneath.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper we talk about the job scheduling for cloud computing condition. By doing research and examination of this issue goes for job allocation with least aggregate undertakings consummation time and least cost. CloudSim3.0.3 is utilized to complete and recreate the task calculation, and conveyed scheduling methods. In this work, we have executed two load adjusting methods named as "Throttled Stack Adjustment Strategy and Active VM Load Balancing Strategy" with top load sharing representatives' frameworks "Optimized Response Time and Reconfigure Dynamically". These arrangements are actualized, and work is executed in the cloudsim 3.0.3 to assess VM_Cost, DC_Cost, Response Time and Data Processing Time of proposed Virtual Machine (VM) stack adjusting calculations and contrasting the outcomes with the default round robin scheduling procedure officially practiced in cloudsim. The outcomes are contrasted and found better than Round Robin scheduling procedure. The conclusion is that the Throttled method of scheduling, when

utilized under Reconfigure Dynamically Service, is better than Round Robin and Active VM Load Balancing strategy.
 In future different, more strategies can be utilized, and approaches can be actualized to upgrade the cost and response

time of the occupations. This enhanced ABC calculation just takes the underlying exploration on assignment scheduling for Cloud stage. However, many issues stay open.

TABLE I
 OPTIMIZE RESPONSE TIME

Data Center	VM_Cost (Round Robin)	VM_Cost (Equally Spread)	VM_Cost (Throttled)	DC_Cost (Round Robin)	DC_Cost (Equally Spread)	DC_Cost (Throttled)	Response Time (Avg.)	DC Processing Time (Avg.)
DC1	0.501	0.501	0.501	0.437	0.429	0.426	286.18(RR)	0.35(RR)
DC2	0.601	0.601	0.601	0.421	0.419	0.419	286.18(EQ)	0.35(EQ)
DC3	0.501	0.501	0.501	0.417	0.427	0.431	286.18(TH)	0.35(TH)

TABLE II
 RECONFIGURE DYNAMICALLY

Data Center	VM_Cost (Round Robin)	VM_Cost (Equally Spread)	VM_Cost (Throttled)	DC_Cost (Round Robin)	DC_Cost (Equally Spread)	DC_Cost (Throttled)	Response Time (Avg.)	DC Processing Time (Avg.)
DC1	3.19	3.27	3.27	0.428	0.422	0.432	288.98(RR)	3.34(RR)
DC2	3.37	3.452	3.452	0.406	0.424	0.430	286.89(EQ)	0.92(EQ)
DC3	3.35	3.255	3.255	0.441	0.429	0.414	286.53(TH)	0.91(TH)

TABLE III
 VM COST EVALUATION

Cloud app service broker	VM COST (RR)	VM COST (TH)	VM COST (EQ)
Optimize Response Time	0.501	0.501	0.501
Reconfigure Dynamically	3.35	3.25	3.25

TABLE IV
 DC COST EVALUATION

Cloud App Service Broker	DC COST (RR)	DC COST (EQ)	DC COST (TH)
Optimize Response Time	0.437	0.429	0.426
Reconfigure Dynamically	0.441	0.429	0.414

TABLE V
 RESPONSE TIME AND DATA PROCESSING TIME EVALUATION

Scheduling policies	Response Time (ORT)	Data Processing Time (ORT)	Response Time (RD)	Data Processing Time (RD)
Round robin	286.18	0.35	288.98	3.34
Equally spread	286.18	0.35	286.56	0.92
Throttled	286.18	0.35	286.53	0.91

Fig. 1 Graphical evaluation of VM_Cost

Fig. 2 DC_Cost Evaluation

Fig. 3 Response Time Evaluations

Fig. 4 Data Processing Time Evaluations

REFERENCES

- [1] Jaspreet Singh, Deepali Gupta “Energy Efficient Heuristic Base Job Scheduling Algorithms in Cloud Computing” IOSR Journal of Computer Engineering (IOSR-JCE) e-ISSN: 2278-0661,p-ISSN: 2278-8727, Volume 19, Issue 1, Ver. I (Jan.-Feb. 2017), PP 50-55.
- [2] RAJA K, SEKAR G. “An Algorithm for Credit Based Scheduling in Cloud Computing Environment Depending Upon Deadline Strategy”. IOSR Journal of Computer Engineering (IOSR-JCE) e-ISSN: 2278-0661, p-ISSN: 2278-8727, Volume 19, Issue 1, Ver. I (Jan.-Feb. 2017), PP 55-65.
- [3] Ashutosh V Kale, Gopal U Tangade, Yogesh J Jadhao, Prof. V.P. Narkhede, Prof. S. M. Dandage “Design and Implementation of load balancing in grid using min-min algorithm” International Journal of Research in Advent Technology (IJRAT) (E-ISSN: 2321-9637)National Conference “CONVERGENCE 2016”, 06th-07th April 2016.
- [4] Anousha S, Ahmadi M. “An improved Min-Min task scheduling algorithm in grid computing”. In International Conference on Grid and Pervasive Computing 2013 May 9 (pp. 103-113). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.

- [5] Boroujerd I, "Efficient Scheduling in Cloud Networks Using Chakoos Evolutionary Algorithm". IOSR Journal of Computer Engineering (IOSR-JCE) e-ISSN: 2278-0661,p-ISSN: 2278-8727, Volume 18, Issue 1, Ver. I (Jan.-Feb. 2017), PP 50-55.
- [6] Oesterle F, Ostermann S, Prodan R, Mayr GJ. "Experiences with distributed computing for meteorological applications grid computing and cloud computing". Geoscientific Model Development. 2015 Jul 13;8(7):2067-78.
- [7] Ajmire D, Atique M. "Grouping Based Load Balancing in Cloud Computing". International Journal of Innovative Research and Development. 2016 Jan 12;5(2).
- [8] Mukundha C, Gayathri P, Prabha IS. "Load Balance Scheduling Algorithm for Serving of Requests in Cloud Networks Using Software Defined Networks". International Journal of Applied Engineering Research. 2016;11(6):3910-4.
- [9] Suri PK, Rani S. "Simulator for Priority based Scheduling of Resources in Cloud Computing". International Journal of Computer Applications. 2016 Jan 1;146(14).
- [10] Mr. F. DestoniusDhiraviam, Mr. Vinoth Raj "Two-Way Cloud Computing in Research and Educational Surroundings using Virtual Cloud" International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research, Volume 6, Issue 2, February-2015 ISSN 2229-5518.